

New Operations with Infinity

1.Dividing one positive integer with zero.

$$\mathbf{a \div 0 = \infty}$$

Explanation:

If we have 5 apples and decide to put 0 apples in a box, the result is that we will have an infinite amount of boxes to “fill” with no apples, and still what remains are the 5 apples we had at the start of our operation.

2.Subtracting infinity with infinity.

$$\infty - \infty = \mathbf{0}$$

Explanation:

Infinity has the property of being absolute, so whenever we use it as a concept, we always have the same property. In simple words, infinity is the same. So in our operation above, the first infinity is the same as the second one, and therefore, since they are the same, the result is logically zero.

3.Infinity divided with infinity.

$$\infty \div \infty = \mathbf{1}$$

Explanation:

As mentioned above, since infinity is always the same with another infinity, dividing them with one another logically outcomes one.

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